

Analyzing the Effect of English Subject Teaching on the English Writing Skills of Secondary School Students

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Vol. V, No. I (Winter 2020)

Pages: 19 – 28

DOI: 10.31703/gesr.2020(V-I).03

Abstract: *English is known as an international language for communication. In Pakistan, English is used as an official language however, the national language of Pakistan is Urdu. In schools, the English language is taught as a compulsory subject. It plays a very important role in developing communication skills among students. The present research is related to analyze the effect of English subject teaching on the writing skills of Secondary School Students in South Punjab. In this research 9th class government and private school were taken as study sample. A writing skill test that was related to English language conducted for collecting the data. After collection of data a comparison chart was made. In this chart difference between both school students was visible. The conclusion was made on the basis of results and in the end, suggestions were given for improving the writing skills of students.*

Key Words: English, Language, Teaching Skills, Secondary School

Introduction

Language is a special gift from God to human beings. An English word “Language” is a Latin word and it is derived from Indo-European word “tongue or speech” (Blommaert, 2010). The word language is on occasion used denoting to secret message or maybe a private discussion. Coleman (2010) defines, language is used to express internal feelings of human beings. It is used to define difficult ideas, thoughts, how to communicate with each other, complete or fulfill requirements along with making rules and sustain our culture. We can say language is elementary component of communication. All languages have some rules and grammar. We must follow that rules for communication (Crystal, 2012). Pierce and Eplin (1999) suggest that language is a verbal behavior that comprises signals and different types of body movement as well as spoken word through which we can communicate with others.

In the twelfth century, a chronicler named Henry of Huntington showed interest in the history of finding unique individualities between human and animals. The only way to communicate with each other was language (Erling & Seargeant, 2013). Because the language is the only way to express their thoughts, ideas, opinions etc. It must be a way through which government or organizations can conduct their thoughts with people of their country. Sapir (2004) suggest that a system of human through which they communicate with each other using different types of signals just like gestures, voice sound, and written symbols is called language. Norton (2010) defines, human language is obtaining complicated system of communication. Language is a primarily human and non-instinctive method of communicating ideas, emotions and desires by means of a system voluntarily produced symbol.

Different types of languages are used in the world. These languages are not only present in our minds or thoughts but also in our daily life discussions, in prayers, in mediations in interactions etc. The main difference between human being and animal is that human can interact with each other through

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language but animals cannot. [Zimmerman, Bonner, and Kovach \(1996\)](#) described language as the tool through which human beings can interact with each other for conveying their messages, thoughts, ideas, and opinions. It is through language that human beings can store their desired knowledge, transfer messages, transfer any type of knowledge or experiences from one person to another person or from one place to another place ([Deignan, 2005](#)). [Ward \(1910\)](#) displayed that language is defined as a method of conservative spoken or through written symbols human being can interact with social community. Language can be defined through expressions that are means of sound of speech ([Henry, 1990](#)).

Every nation has its own personal language and identity that makes it different from other nations. [Camenson \(2007\)](#) argued that English is an international language is mostly used and considered as common language. Presently, most knowledge of the universe is in English language and most of researchers use English language for presenting their research findings. Nowadays a person unable to understand or speak English, faces many difficulties or problem and sometimes he/she is assumed to be illiterate ([Khojasteh & Nadernia, 2016](#)). Most of the articles published on internet are in English. If we want to match pace with the world we have to speak and understand English. If a person who wants a well-paid job or move for higher qualification, he/she must be able to speak English.

The approach people use to converse, carry out business and invention of scientific technology are worthy studying. It is apparent that not everyone can be a philosopher or linguistic scholar (Hayes, 2017). But it cannot be denied that educated person must be aware of structure of his or her language, its ranking in this world and its relation to other tongues, affluence of its vocabulary and different varieties of speech gathered under single name of English language. Diverse culture depicted in the language represents the long history of English of about 100 years ago. It is quite clear that political, economic and social forces impact a language ([Jenkins, 2007](#)). These aspects give a language in its shapes, most obviously in the number and spread of its speakers, which is called the sociology of the language.

In the modern age, English language plays an very important role in the development of a nation. All the official work; official mails, official letters, memo etc. all are in English language. Similarly, in education field (schools, colleges and universities), all records are in English ([Manan, 2016](#)). Good conversations or communication is not only making an impact on our personality, but it is also making an effect on our place in the public.

In Pakistan, government schools are mostly Urdu medium and students in colleges faced problems in English courses. Due to this issue student obtained very low scores in those English courses. We can say English is breakthrough to achieve success in mostly field of life. In Pakistan English is used as an official language and Urdu is national language ([Manan & David, 2014](#)). In private schools, most of the syllabus is in English but in government schools, it is in Urdu. The students of private schools are good in English as compared to government school students. Due to this reason most of students have lack of knowledge and they are unable to get the universal knowledge. In simple words, English is a language that is used as a national language in many countries and also used as an official language in many under developed countries like Pakistan, India etc. English language has a momentous place in Pakistani educational system. It is a compulsory subject at all levels in schools, colleges and in universities. Schools prepare all the students for high level education like colleges and universities. The curriculum related to English language is founded on English skills like reading, writing, and spoken English ([Haidar & Fang, 2019](#)). In Pakistan, English language was known as an official language around 1970's to 1980's. According to a survey, almost 30% of Pakistani population is able to communicate with each other in English. It is an essential language for getting high professional position.

Writing skills and inscription abilities are a significant piece of correspondence and communication procedure through which individuals can communicate their musings, sentiments, and views in writing. [Nunan \(2003\)](#) defines: "writing or inscription is related to both corporeal and intellectual performance. At the most essential level, it is the physical demonstration of submitting words or thoughts to some medium. Then again, writing is the psychological or intellectual work of concocting thoughts, considering how to communicate them, and sorting out them into statements, proclamations and sections that will be obvious to a reader." [Shokrpour and Fallahzadeh \(2007\)](#) proposed that writing is not just an intellectual or psychological movement yet in addition a mind-boggling social activity. It is the

impression of the author's ability through relational abilities. It is difficult to acquire and create writing aptitudes, particularly in figuring out how to compose English as a subsequent second language.

Before 1960, the inscription abilities or writing skills of an unknown or foreign dialect habitually did not draw in much consideration; nevertheless, in current years it has been increasingly perceptible and thought about a significant aptitude of correspondence or communication and major substance during the time spent learning a language (Anh, 2019). Accentuating the significance of writing skills, Harmer (2006) stated: "the purposes behind instructing keeping in touch with learners of English as a foreign dialect incorporate fortification, language improvement, learning style, and above all, writing as an aptitude in its own right." It is well known that writing skills or inscription abilities are frequently the least most loved aptitudes of students and the achievement in refining and enhancing writing aptitudes relies upon the accomplishment of the other language aptitudes. Nonetheless, writing skills or inscription aptitudes cannot be ignored since it is a significant ability in everyday life just as scholarly exercises. When students are acceptable and good at writing effectively and sensibly, they will realize how to utilize suitable language and style in their examination, study and work later on (Dwivedi, 2015).

Now the question is what is curriculum? Curriculum is basically a Latin word. It is a course or a subject specifically related to a topic like English, English grammar etc. That student studied in school colleges or universities. English curriculum is a subject that specifically related to English and its rules. Those rules describe how to speak English and how to communicate with each other and how to read and write. There are certain rules for writing English. Every person who want to write in English must follow those rules (Baugh & Cable, 2002). Writing is the way of communication or interaction that allows persons to express their thoughts, ideas and feelings on a piece of paper, to start up their awareness and principles into undoubted arguments. In its progressive form, as a child learns the basic steps of writing simple words and then writing simple sentences and after this, these sentences will expand in the form of stories, letters, essays (Graddol, 1997). Grammar rules, spelling and vocabulary join together to make writing easy. After the definition of writing, writing skills must be defined as the talent to change ideas into proper sentences with the help of proper rules and regulations.

Research Methodology

Research means to find or investigate some topics in detail and research methodology is systematic to analyze the topic. The nature of this study is Quantitative. The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of English subject teaching on the English writing skills of secondary school students in South Punjab. In this study, total 50 students were selected conveniently from 10 schools (05 government and 05 private). From every school, 05 students were randomly selected from 9th class that made the sample of 25 students from government and 25 students from private schools.

For comparing the students' performance in English writing skills, a test was prepared from 9th class English subject book that was validated with expert opinions. This test was related to English writing skills and developed to find out the difficulties and differences between government school and private school students. The test consisted of select correct sentences and fill in the blank with correct missing letter of 30 marks, word sentence consisted of 05 marks, story writing consisted of 10 marks and creative writing consisted of 05 marks. The whole test total was 50 scores. For purpose of taking tests from students, the sampled students were divided into two groups one was having 25 students of government school and other was 25 students from private schools. The question type tool that is used in this study is mostly used and a very common research method. After this full process and meeting that was held with principal the required test was conducted. First, the scholar went to the government schools and managed a writing skill test on male and female students. After this, exactly the same test was managed on the students of private school. The strength of this test was kept according to the purposes of the research and this test was checked by the subject specialist of English, teaching in different government and private schools at secondary level.

Results

The test contained five questions. The first question consisted of circling the correct option or sentence in which subject, verb and object and fill in the blank with correct missing letter (30 scores), second

question is about word sentences, in this question a word is given and uses the word correctly in the sentence (05 scores), third question in about a story writing in this question a picture is given and students made the story according to the picture (10 scores), and the last question was about creative writing (05 scores). After test, the data was gathered and analyzed in MS Excel and SPSS 20th in the form of graphs and tables.

Table 1. Scores of Private School Students in Test

Roll #	Obtained Scores in Q # 1 out of (30)	Obtained Scores in Q # 2 out of (5)	Obtained Scores in Q # 3 out of (10)	Obtained Scores in Q # 4 out of (5)	Total Scores
1	23.00	5.00	9.00	4.00	41.00
2	24.00	5.00	9.00	4.00	42.00
3	24.00	4.00	10.00	3.00	41.00
4	24.00	4.00	9.00	3.00	40.00
5	24.00	4.00	9.00	3.00	40.00
6	24.00	5.00	9.00	4.00	42.00
7	24.00	3.00	8.00	3.00	38.00
8	24.00	5.00	9.00	3.00	41.00
9	24.00	4.00	9.00	3.00	40.00
10	25.00	4.00	9.00	3.00	41.00
11	22.00	3.00	9.00	3.00	37.00
12	24.00	3.00	8.00	1.00	36.00
13	24.00	3.00	9.00	2.00	38.00
14	24.00	3.00	9.00	2.00	38.00
15	23.00	3.00	9.00	1.00	36.00
16	23.00	3.00	9.00	1.00	36.00
17	25.00	4.00	9.00	4.00	42.00
18	23.00	2.00	10.00	1.00	36.00
19	24.00	4.00	9.00	2.00	39.00
20	21.00	2.00	9.00	2.00	34.00
21	25.00	3.00	9.00	3.00	40.00
22	24.00	4.00	10.00	2.00	40.00
23	20.00	4.00	10.00	2.00	36.00
24	21.00	3.00	9.00	3.00	36.00
25	22.00	3.00	8.00	1.00	34.00
Mean	23.40	3.60	9.04	2.52	38.56

The scores of private schools' students that are collected through a written test are presented in Table 1. In 1st question having 30 scores, most of students obtained 24 scores. While 03 students obtained 25 scores. Four students obtained 23 scores, two students obtained 22 scores, two students obtained 21 scores and one student obtained 20 scores. If we calculate overall performance in question no 1 that is good mostly students obtained 80% scores with mean score of ($M = 23.40$). In 2nd question, four students obtained 100% scores 5 out of 5. Mostly students obtained 4 scores out of 5 scores and their percentage is 80%. Ten students obtained 3 scores out of 5 and their percentage is 60%. If we calculate mean score of second question that is ($M = 3.60$). In 3rd question, that was concerned with the story writing through picture, students made a story that was related to Greedy dog or Greed is a Curse, mostly students obtained 9 out of 10 and their percentage is 90%. Then four students obtained 10 out of 10 and their percentage is 100%, while 3 students obtained 8 scores and overall mean score of this question was ($M = 9.04$). The last question was related to creative writing and they wrote an essay on my hobby. In 4th question, mostly students obtained average scores 3 out of 5. But the result of some students was really bad they obtained only 1 mark in this question. Few students obtained 80% scores in this question. If we calculate mean of this question that was ($M = 2.52$). The highest score obtained by students was 45 and this score obtained by only 1 student. The second highest score was 42 by 3 students, four students obtained 41 scores, 5 students obtained 40 out of 50. 1 student obtained 39 and three students obtained

38 scores. 1 student obtained 37 scores, 3 students obtained 36 scores, 3 students obtained 35 scores and one student obtained 34 scores. If we calculate overall mean score that was ($M = 38.56$).

Table 2. Scores of Government School Students in Test

Roll #	Obtained Scores in Q # 1 out of (30)	Obtained Scores in Q # 2 out of (5)	Obtained Scores in Q # 3 out of (10)	Obtained Scores in Q # 4 out of (5)	Total Scores
1	23.00	2.00	8.00	1.00	34.00
2	24.00	2.00	8.00	2.00	36.00
3	22.00	2.00	7.00	1.00	32.00
4	21.00	1.00	6.00	2.00	30.00
5	22.00	2.00	6.00	1.00	31.00
6	23.00	2.00	1.00	4.00	30.00
7	23.00	1.00	2.00	3.00	29.00
8	23.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	24.00
9	20.00	0.00	2.00	1.00	23.00
10	18.00	0.00	1.00	3.00	22.00
11	21.00	2.00	4.00	4.00	31.00
12	23.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	30.00
13	19.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	22.00
14	23.00	1.00	1.00	3.00	28.00
15	19.00	2.00	0.00	2.00	23.00
16	23.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	27.00
17	22.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	27.00
18	21.00	2.00	4.00	2.00	29.00
19	23.00	2.00	2.00	4.00	31.00
20	22.00	3.00	1.00	2.00	28.00
21	21.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	26.00
22	24.00	4.00	3.00	0.00	31.00
23	21.00	2.00	6.00	1.00	30.00
24	21.00	1.00	6.00	1.00	29.00
25	24.00	2.00	5.00	2.00	33.00
Mean	21.84	1.68	3.24	1.88	28.64

The scores of government schools' students that are collected through a written test are presented in Table 2. In 1st question, out of 30, mostly students scored 24. Three students scored 24. Eight students obtained 23 scores, four students obtained 22 scores, six students obtained 21 scores, one student obtained 20 scores, two students obtained 19 scores and one student obtained 18 scores. If we calculate mean score in 1st question that ($M = 21.84$). In 2nd question, mostly students obtained 2 score out of 5 and their percentage is 40%. One student obtained 4 score. One student obtained 3 score out of 5 and their percentage is 60%. Fourteen students obtained 2 out of 5, seven students obtained 1 out of 5 and two students obtained zero score. If we calculate mean of second question that is ($M = 1.68$). In 3rd question, mostly students scored 2 out of 5. But the result of some students was really bad they obtained 0 scores in this question. Two students obtained 0 scores, six students obtained 1 mark, six students obtained 2 score, one student obtained 3 scores, two students obtained 4 scores, and one student obtained 5 scores. Four students obtained 6 scores. One student obtained 7 scores. Two students obtained 8 scores. If we calculate mean of this question that was ($M = 3.24$). In 4th question, two students obtained 0 scores, nine students obtained 1 mark, and seven students obtained 2 scores, four students obtained 3 scores and 3 students obtained 4 scores. If we calculate mean of this question that was ($M = 1.88$). The highest scores by students was 36 and this score was obtained by only 1 student. The second highest score was 34 by only 1 student, and one student scored 33. Three students obtained 31 scores, three students obtained 30 scores, and lowest scores were 20. The overall mean score was ($M = 28.64$).

Table 3. Difference between Mean Score of Govt and Private School Students in all Questions

	N	Government		Private	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Question # 01	25	21.84	1.50	23.40	1.30
Question # 02	25	1.68	11.60	3.60	10.70
Question # 03	25	3.24	10.84	9.04	8.00
Question # 04	25	1.88	11.05	2.52	11.24
Average Score		28.64	6.95	38.56	4.88

The mean difference between government and private students in question one is depicted in figure 1. This shows the performance related to circling the correct option or sentence in which subject, verb and object and fill in the blank with correct missing letter and correct use of verbs. The mean score of private school students was ($M = 23.40, SD = 1.3$) and government school students was ($M = 21.84, SD = 1.5$). The students of government school lacked an understanding related to subject, verb and object and filling in the blank with correct missing letter etc.

Figure 1. Mean Difference between GS and PS Students' test score in Q# 1

The mean difference between government and private students in question two is depicted in figure 2. This shows the performance related to word sentences. The mean score of private school students was ($M = 3.60, SD = 10.70$) and government school students was ($M = 1.68, SD = 11.60$). The students of Government school must develop an understanding related to word sentence or uses the word correctly in the sentence etc.

Figure 2. Mean Difference between GS and PS Students' test score in Q# 2

The mean difference between government and private students in question three is depicted in figure 3. This shows the performance related to write a story according to picture. The mean score of private school students was ($M = 9.04, SD = 8.00$) and government school students was ($M = 3.24, SD = 10.84$). The students of Government school must develop an understanding related to story writing.

Figure 3. Mean Difference between GS and PS Students' test score in Q# 3

The mean difference between government and private students in question four is depicted in figure 4. This shows the performance related to comprehensive writing. The mean score of private school students was ($M = 2.52, SD = 11.24$) and government school students was ($M = 1.88, SD = 11.05$). The students of government school must develop an understanding related to comprehensive writing etc.

Figure 4. Mean Difference between GS and PS Students' test score in Q# 4

The mean difference between government and private students in all questions shows clearly difference between government school students and private school students. The mean score of private school students was ($M = 38.56, SD = 4.88$) and government school students was ($M = 28.64, SD = 6.95$). The students of Government school must develop an understanding related to English writing skills.

Discussion

Based on the study results, it is evident that the students of government school lack an understanding related to verbs etc. which they must develop. The findings of [Anh \(2019\)](#) also supported our results and proposed that it is essential to raise learners' attention to the significance of English writing aptitudes and the writing module in the preliminary English classes as inscription or writing is a significant device for clients to impart in an assortment of ways. At the point when English learners can compose well, they will have the option to talk well and advance and enhance reading capacity all the more successfully ([Nguyen, 2015](#)). Also, acing writing aptitudes will assist students with improving their capacity to utilize grammar, vocabulary and syntax, accordingly building up their own language abilities.

The findings related to word sentences revealed that the students of government school must develop an understanding related to sentence structure, vocabulary and grammar because in this question only four students obtained 100% scores. The similar results were obtained in the study of [Eisterhold \(1997\)](#) and [Anh \(2019\)](#) suggested that the requirement for viable vocabulary, grammar and syntax learning is additionally stressed since vocabulary, grammar and punctuation are firmly connected with writing. Vocabulary assumes a significant job to support students to utilize an unknown or foreign dialect while acing sentence structure and grammar rules assist learners to convey thoughts, sentiments, and considerations precisely and viably whether as verbal or written correspondence. A decent scope of

syntactic standards can be the keys to assist learners with perceiving the slip-ups and improve the inscriptive standard.

Moreover, the study results expressed that students of government school must develop an understanding related to story writing and comprehensive writing. The results of the study conducted by [Nguyen \(2011\)](#) are also in-line with the findings of this study investigated that broaden reading exercises in English are additionally the subject to be proposed. Unmistakably reading and inscription consistently have close and corresponding connections. In this way, to create and develop viable and strong writing abilities, learners need to extend their perusing and reading exercises ([Kasper, 1998](#)). By reading different documents such as perception of archives, writings or papers in English, learners will have the option to both improve their grammar, vocabulary and syntax knowledge and learn more approaches to communicate their thoughts. This study results are further consistent with the study findings of [Tran \(2007\)](#) when contemplating the learning inspiration of Vietnamese learners in English writing classes. In like manner, for quite a while, instructing language structure, grammar, vocabulary and sentence structure have been considered as the center in English writing aptitudes exercises in Vietnam, which causes learners to misjudge the genuine idea of figuring out how to compose and the real nature of learning to write.

Conclusion

In conclusion of the overall findings related to the study, it can be said that writing and inscription expertise is one of the four fundamental and vital abilities in teaching learning process and utilizing English. Writing or inscription is usually viewed as the most troublesome and exhausting exercise however, this is as yet a significant aptitude student needs to get a handle on. The study results manifest that the inscription abilities and aptitudes of students are exceptionally restricted and did not meet the expectations and desires. Learners themselves have no feeling of mindfulness and activity in the subject. In completing the test, students face numerous challenges in grammar, sentence structure, vocabulary, essay writing and story writing and unable to apply any significant bearing or writing strategies or any adaptable inscriptive systems successfully. The reason for the troubles originates from the abstract side of the students themselves and objectivity because of the components of learning content and teaching techniques.

From examining the students' basic inscriptive and writing botches, their challenges in working on writing and the sources, the study exploration proposes workable solutions to enhance and progress the English writing abilities of the secondary level learners. Likewise, it helps improve the viability of the educating and learning of writing and inscription abilities in the English subject teaching and educational program for the top-notch at South Punjab, Pakistan. It is highly recommended that students must understand the importance of writing skills in their studies and practice more and more to get expertise in these skills. They must also understand that these skills are also very useful for their own learning and work later on. Teachers must improve teaching techniques and differentiate learning exercises to pull in learners to examine and improve inscriptive aptitudes; and solution for the educational plan and instructing materials. In conclusion, we can say that the students of government school must develop an understanding related to English language writing skills. At the end the researcher came to find out that there is a lack of interest in English language mostly in government school students. They use key books or guide books for guidance. They need much more practice to overcome this fault. Teachers must motivate students and having short sessions for practice.

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